

SoildiverAgro project

Adoption of new management practices to increase crop production and quality

THE WHAT AND WHY

Soil organic carbon stocks in agricultural fields in Flanders are extremely low

Organic matter has many, important functions in soil. They are a food source for soil life, they improve structure, promote workability, increase soil moisture retention, and they are a source of crop nutrients. Increasing the organic carbon content

in the topsoil is therefore very interesting from an agricultural point of view. However, a decline in organic carbon stocks has been observed since 1990 in Flanders, with extremely low values even being observed in some places.

HOW IS THE CHALLENGE ADDRESSED

Non-tilling operations and compost increase organic carbon in the topsoil

Adaptations to the agricultural system can address this problem. In Flanders, it appears that many farmers are already applying non-tilling to preserve the fertile top layer of the soil, avoid erosion and not disturb soil life. Other farmers have doubts about these practices because they fear high weed pressure, compacted soil layers, too moist soils in wet weather conditions, crop residues remaining on the field or a seed bed that is too coarse. During a multi-year field experiment with potatoes, cereals and vegetables, among others, it was

found that non-tilling soil practices still keeps weed growth manageable, soil layers can be sufficiently mixed and crop residues can be incorporated. Importantly, it was also confirmed that in Flanders too, more organic carbon accumulates in the top layer with non-inversion tillage in combination with, among others, the application of compost. Although confirmation is needed in the long term, in the short term this practice appears to have a beneficial effect on a problematic soil-organic carbon deficiency in agricultural fields.

1. Some non-tillage soil mechanical treatments applied on the experimental field. Left: weed control, right: destroying and (partial) incorporation of crop remnants (ILVO).

KEYWORDS

Compost, non-tillage practices, organic carbon stocks

AUTHORSHIP

Lieven Waeyenberge, Flanders Research Institute for Agriculture, Fisheries and Food (ILVO) Merelbeke, Belgium.

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